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Editorial

Human Well-Being and Flourishing

It was the French philosopher Paul Ricoeur has masters of suspicion. From there on he struggled with both “hermeneutics of suspicion” and then “hermeneutics of trust.”

In his *Freud and Philosophy* (1965) Paul Ricœur proposed the “hermeneutics of suspicion” to capture a common spirit that pervades the critical writings of Karl Marx, Sigmund Freud, and Friedrich Nietzsche, whom he calls the three “masters of suspicion”.

While a hermeneutic of suspicion reduces the extraordinary to the ordinary, a hermeneutic of trust employs a more empathetic approach, one that attempts to reconstruct the historical worlds in which their subjects lived. In our day-to-day lives, though they appear paradoxical, there are ways to trust and critique simultaneously. It helps scholars to reconstruct worldviews that are meaningful and creative for a community. It enables a

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community to critique its common guidelines and at the same time to be committed to the values and vision of the community.

Paul Ricoeur has also introduced the rich notion of “second naïveté.” He has dared to interpret ancient myths and metaphors, which are able to offer illuminating and fruitful understandings of the human condition. For this after critiquing everything, we need to rediscover the richness and profundity of “second naïveté.” After having gone through the painful search, the “second naïveté” enables us to grasp the others and community with trust, in spite of their weakness and vulnerabilities.

It may be noted that Dr Cyril Desbruslais, SJ, whom we honour in this issue of *Jnanadeepa*, has been an ardent follower of Paul Ricoeur. He is turned 75 on December 21, 2015. So this special volume of the journal is to honour his contribution to philosophy in general and philosophy of liberation in particular.

The critical side of Ricoeur’s philosophy as applied to Desbruslais was taken up earlier in *Jnanadeepa* (2012, Vol 15). So this special issue of the journal takes up the creative and flourishing dimensions of human life, to which Dr Desbruslais has been passionately attached. His philosophy of liberation is plea for human flourishing with passion and compassion.

All the articles in this volume celebrate human well-being and flourishing with critical and cautious trust!

May this volume of the *Jnanadeepa* help us to reach out to others in compassion and commit ourselves for the well-being of all, including the non-human creation!

The Editor